

Carbon nanostructures for flexible and high efficiency energy application

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1. Abstract

Advent of nanotechnology has generated huge interest in application of carbon-based nanomaterials as future energy materials such as a possible replacement for conventionally used graphite as anode of Li-ion batteries and a new flexible and high efficiency electrode system. This talk will focus on engineering of carbon nanomaterials, graphene and carbon nanotubes (CNTs), and their applications in Li-ion battery and flexible solar cells. Various organized architectures of carbon nanomaterials can be fabricated using interfacial control and direct self assembly of these structures. Our recent development of 3-dimensional carbon nanostructural anode will be highlighted. The unique 3D design of the electrode allowed much higher solid loading of active anode material, CNTs in this case and resulted in more amount of Li⁺ ion intake in comparison to those of conventional 2D anode. Though one such 3D anode was demonstrated to offer 50% higher capacity, compared to its 2D counterpart, its ability to deliver much higher capacity, by geometrical modification, is presented. Our recent results of bonding energy characterization of graphene and CNTs with their substrates will be introduced to offer the optimum structure of carbon nanomaterials.

2. Results and Discussion

2.1 3D CNTs electrode for Li-ion Battery

Carbon nanotubes, in different forms and architectures, have demonstrated good promise as electrode material for Li-ion batteries, owing to large surface area, shorter Li-conduction distance and high electrical conductivity. However, practical application of such Li-ion batteries demands higher volumetric capacity, which is otherwise low for most nanomaterials, used as electrodes. In order to address this urgent issue, we have developed a novel 3-dimensional (3D) anode, based on multiwall

carbon nanotubes (MWCNTs), for Li-ion batteries. The unique 3D design of the electrode allowed much higher solid loading of active anode material, MWCNTs in this case and resulted in more amount of Li⁺ ion intake in comparison to those of conventional 2D Cu current collector. Though one such 3D anode was demonstrated to offer 50% higher capacity, compared to its 2D counterpart, its ability to deliver much higher capacity, by geometrical modification, is presented. Furthermore, deposition of amorphous Si (a-Si) layer on the 3D electrode (a-Si/MWCNTs hybrid structure) offered enhancement in electrochemical response.

Fig. 1 A schematic model of an anode stack assembled using 4 numbers of converted uniform stacking cuboid arrays from the geometry of a real 3D Cu mesh (right) SEM images exhibiting a cross-section perpendicular to the anode system.

Fig. 2 Electrochemical performance of the anode structures of as-grown MWCNTs on 3D Cu mesh, MWCNTs on 2D Cu foil and a-Si/MWCNTs core-shell composite on 3D Cu mesh.

2.2 3D Field Emitter

Developing a high-current field emitter with high operational stability is in demand for a number of applications, including x-ray, electron microscopes, flat panel display and high power microwave generators, and thus, has been the focus of many researchers in the last decade. This need can be fulfilled by application of engineered nanomaterials and novel designing of electron emitters. In the present research, a field emitter is designed and fabricated for high-current electron emission applications, involving growth of interface controlled carbon nanotubes along micro-channels of three dimensional (3-D) copper template. Field emission characterization of the emitter shows very high emission current density (270 mA/cm², peak), along with low turn-on field (1.1 V/μm), low threshold field (1.69 V/μm), excellent long-term emission stability for extended hours of operation and excellent resistance to structural damage. While higher conductivity of the copper substrate, lower CNT-substrate interfacial resistance and strong interfacial bonding between Cu and CNTs are responsible for superior field emission properties, unique 3-D design elevates number of emission sites and provides protection against structural damage from ion bombardment and arcing, leading to 23-27 times higher emission current density. Novel design, excellent properties and a simple three-step processing route make this CNT-based emitter open a new era for high current-density field emission devices.

Fig. 3 Field emission response of 3D cathode structure (numbers mentioned within the plots are the number of micro-channels in corresponding samples).

2.3 Graphene Based Flexible Solar Cells

We demonstrated the synthesis of large scale graphene by thermal chemical vapor deposition

method, and explore chemical doping of p-type donors (HNO₃) in graphene lattice. Using X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy we affirms that different C-H and NO₃⁻ moieties were covalently attached with carbon atoms through sp²-sp³ hybridization with graphene matrix. Furthermore, we successfully demonstrated that the systematic formation of C-O and C=O covalent bond with different concentration of HNO₃ which facilitate the different amount protonation (p-type carriers) in the graphene crystal. Moreover, we observed the Fermi level shift in nitric acid doped graphene using ultraviolet photoemission spectroscopy (UPS) which illustrates the controlled Fermi level pinning from 4.52 to 5.31 eV under different concentration of HNO₃ doping. Furthermore, dye-sensitized solar cells (DSCs) comprising HDG counter electrodes exhibited 3.2% photo-conversion efficiency than PG electrodes (~1.2%), which we believe due to the improvement of in-plane charge transfer of basal planes which further fortify the electrocatalytic activity of acid doped graphene. In particular, control over the charge diffusivity of redox species at the counter electrode and surface charge transfer resistance due to the acid doping in graphene offers enormous new insights of catalytic electrode development opportunities for electro catalytic devices.

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